

Submitted Manuscript

Chromatographic propane-propylene separation by different zeolites obtained from rice husk ashes

Katia Borrego Morales¹, Daniel Ballesteros-Plata², Enrique Rodríguez-Castellón², Juan A. Cecilia², A. Rabdel Ruiz-Salvador^{3,4}, Giselle I. Autié Castro^{1*}, Tania Farías^{1*}

¹ *Institute of Materials Science and Technology (IMRE), University of Havana, Havana, Cuba*

² *Departamento de Química Inorgánica, Cristalografía y Mineralogía, Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Málaga, Málaga, Spain*

³ *Departamento de Sistemas Físicos, Químicos y Naturales, Facultad de Ciencias Experimentales, Universidad Pablo de Olavide, Seville, Spain*

⁴ *Centro de Nanociencia y Tecnologías Sostenibles (CNATS), Universidad Pablo de Olavide, Carretera de Utrera km. 1, Seville, E-41013, Spain*

* *Correspondence: gautie@imre.uh.cu, giselleautie@gmail.com, Tel.: +(53) 78707666*

tania@imre.uh.cu, fariascu@gmail.com, Tel.: +(53) 78707666

ABSTRACT

Chromatographic separation of propane and propylene is accomplished by three low-cost zeolite X (microporous, hierarchical and acidic). The materials were synthesized from rice husk ash, and characterized by X-ray powder diffraction, high-resolution transmission and scanning electron microscopies, N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms at -196 °C, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy, infra-red spectroscopy and thermogravimetric analysis. From chromatographic data, the differential adsorption heats involved, the separation factors and the corresponding partition coefficients were estimated. Preferential adsorption of propylene was found in all samples and also favorable separation factors were computed for the studied separation. The higher interaction energy values were obtained for the hierarchical zeolite possessing a wide range of micro and mesopores. The results indicate the potential of these materials obtained from an agro-industrial waste for the separation of propane-propylene mixtures.

Keywords: *Inverse gas chromatography, synthetic zeolites, porosity, propane-propylene, separation*

Introduction

Propylene is an important olefin used to produce a wide variety of products in the plastics industry, such as: polypropylene, acrylonitrile, propylene oxide and acrylic acid; and it is also employed in motor fuels for octane improvement [1]. This compound is usually obtained by steam cracking of naphtha, as well as by-product of fluid catalytic cracking of gas in refineries [2]. In this way, different propane-propylene mixtures are obtained in these procedures, where separation by distillation to obtain polymer-grade propylene (99.8-99.9 % purity) is difficult and requires a lot of energy [3]. In industry, these gases are separated in a distillation tower (C3 splitter), which operates at extremely low relative volatilities. To achieve the desired high purities, the distillation tower contains a large number of theoretical plates and operates at large reflux/feed ratios [3]. Reducing cost for propane/propylene industrial separation processes is highly desired, and hence, the search of methods other than distillation is a topic of non-stopping research.

Molecular separation processes based on adsorption are gaining notoriety, both in number and variety, with the goal of lowering cost and the impulse linked to the great development of adsorbent materials [4]. Interesting separation processes have been reported in zeolites, MOFs, mesoporous silica like SBA-15, activated carbons, silica gel, among others [5], [6], [7], [8], [9]. The huge volumes associated with the propane/propylene separation demand robust and easy to prepare adsorbent materials, placing zeolites in a special situation. These are microporous crystalline materials widely used as adsorbents, catalysts and ion exchangers [10].

It is well known that adsorption mechanisms in zeolites depend on many parameters, the most important being pore size features, Si/Al ratio, exchangeable cations, and channel connectivity. For example, the pore size opening in the structure regulates which molecules can access the interior of the channels (size exclusion) and thus diffuse through the channel system. Different authors have studied the use of zeolites such as mordenite, β -Zeolite, ZSM-22, Zeolite X, Zeolite Y, and ZSM-5 in gas mixtures separations [11], [12], [13]. Among them, the works of Huddersman and Klimczyk could be highlighted. These authors studied the separation of 2,3-dimethylbutane and 2-methylheptane with mordenite and β -Zeolite [14]. In addition, Funke *et al.* studied the separation of *n*-octane, iso-octane and *n*-hexane with a Silicalite-1 membrane [15]. These are medium size molecules, where both size exclusion and molecular packing contribute greatly to the separation process. The separation becomes more difficult for small size molecules such

as propane, propylene and other smaller ones. In this context, some important works using zeolites have been reported for their separation [16], [17], [18], [19], [20], [21], [22], [23]. The nature of the extra-framework cations, Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and Ag^+ , has been identified as one of the crucial factors influencing the performance of this separation, where the materials usually show selectivity toward propylene [1], [5], [24], [25].

In the way to improving economic value, the use of a low-cost silica source for preparing large volumes of zeolites is an important avenue. For example, different type of zeolites can be prepared from ashes from agriculture, metallurgy and other sources [26], [27]. The synthesized zeolites obtained by this way usually require a detailed characterization of its textural and structural features prior their use in applications. We must consider that the metastable nature of these materials can account for a wide variability on the final properties associated to minor modifications of experimental conditions, including the silicon source [28], [29]. In the case of using agriculture ashes, the presence of impurities plays an important role in the kinetic and thermodynamic of the synthesis reaction [30]. Rice husk ashes are produced in large quantities and represent an environmental problem. At the same time, it is known that these wastes exhibit silica content above 60 wt.% reaching values even of 97 wt.%, which has stimulated their use for synthesizing zeolites [31], [32], [33], [34], [35]. Another factor that can be relevant for industrial separation is the kinetics of the diffusing molecules, being a key parameter in speeding the process. Fast overall diffusion could be attained by providing the zeolite with a hierarchical porosity with the inclusion of mesoporosity [36], [37], [38].

Inverse gas chromatography (IGC) is a well-established technique for surface characterization of materials [39], [40], particularly using the zero surface coverage or infinity dilution (IGC-ID) method, where the role of adsorbate–adsorbate interactions are minimized. In this method, the chromatographic principle is inverted since the “unknown material” (synthetic zeolites in this work) is placed as the stationary phase. Thus, using well-known probe molecules, the nature of adsorbate–adsorbent interactions can be estimated. The required equipment is a standard gas chromatograph equipped with a short column packed with the material to be studied. The main parameter obtained is the retention time value, which allows determining the net retention volume and finally the adsorption heat. IGC-ID has been previously used by some of us to evaluate the separation ability of *n*-paraffins, propane-propylene and benzene-toluene-xylene (BTX) by hexacyanocobaltates, Cu-BTC, Fe-BTC MOFs, and clinoptilolite [41], [42], [43], [44].

Given this background, the aim of the present work is to study the separation of propane and propylene by three synthetic type X zeolites (microporous, hierarchical and acidic) synthesized from an agro-industrial waste (rice husk ashes). To this end, the adsorption features are considered and also the differences among the textural, crystalline and morphological characteristics of the solids. One motivation of using zeolite X is that the relative large pore size allows moderately fast diffusion, as compared to small pore size zeolites that can separate propane/propylene mixtures by size exclusion [22], [45], but it is expected to occur at the cost of small diffusivity of propylene. To the best of our knowledge, no acidic and/or hierarchical zeolite X samples have been studied for the separation of this mixture.

Materials and methods

Samples preparation

Three zeolites were obtained: zeolite X (ZSX), hierarchical zeolite X (ZSX-J) and acidic zeolite X (ZSX-H). All syntheses started from rice husk ash (RHA) as a source of silicon. Rice husk (RH) sample of Cuban production (variety M-10, wet season, harvested 15 days after flowering), was kindly supplied by the Cuban Research Institute of Grain. The procedure reported by Borrego-Morales *et al.* [35] was followed for conditioning the RH and obtain the ash. In brief, the RH was washed with water and 1 M HCl to remove mud, dust and metallic impurities and calcined at 700 °C for 2 hours in a muffle to obtain the RHA. The ashes (about 1 g) were placed in a plastic flask and 10 mL of 2 M sodium hydroxide (NaOH, ProLABO, 98%) solution were added for silicon extraction. The mixture was stirred for 4 hours on a magnetic stirrer using a water bath at temperature of 60 °C. After this time, it was allowed to cool and the supernatant solution (containing the sodium silicate) was separated by centrifugation at 1100 rpm and stored in a plastic flask to be used in the synthesis of the zeolites. The remaining solid was washed with deionized water to remove NaOH until pH = 7 and dried at 100 °C in an oven. The amount of silicon extracted was determined by the difference of weight. The silica content in these ashes is usually greater than 95%.

For the synthesis of ZSX, about 0.9 g of sodium aluminate (NaAlO_2 , Sigma-Aldrich, 99%) were weighed and dissolved in a solution of 2 M NaOH and deionized water to obtain a Si/Al molar ratio equal to 2. The sodium silicate solution extracted from the RHA

was slowly added to the sodium aluminate solution while stirring vigorously to achieve the synthesis gel with a composition of $2.89\text{Na}_2\text{O} : \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 : 2\text{SiO}_2 : 145\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Then the reaction was carried out in a conventional oven under static conditions at $90\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 12 hours. After the crystallization time had elapsed, the solid was separated by centrifugation at 1100 rpm. Subsequently, several washes were carried out with deionized water until a pH of about 9. Finally, the solid was dried at $100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in a conventional oven. In the case of ZSX-J, the same procedure was used but adding benzyl-dimethyl-hexadecyl ammonium chloride ($\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{15}\text{N}(\text{Cl})(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, Sigma-Aldrich, $\geq 98\%$) to the gel, and it was aged for 20 days before the reaction. This reagent was used as a template to create mesoporosity, with a concentration in the synthesis gel of 3.5 times the value of its critical micellar concentration ($\text{CMC} = 0.5\text{ mM}$). Finally, ZSX-H was obtained by ammonium ion exchange of ZSX (0.5 M , 24 hours, room temperature) followed by calcination at $450\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (heating rate of $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$) in a conventional furnace.

Characterization of the samples

X-ray powder diffraction patterns of the samples were taken on a X'Pert diffractometer, using nickel filtered $\text{CuK}\alpha$ x-ray source at a scanning rate of 0.02° s^{-1} over the range between 5.0 to 40.0° .

The morphological study of the samples was carried out using a High-Resolution Transmission Electron Microscopy (HRTEM) (TALOS F200x instrument), which also operates in STEM mode (Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy). The equipment also has a HAADF detector, at 200 kV and 200 nA . Microanalysis was carried out with an EDX Super-X system provided with 4 X-ray detectors and an X-FEG beam. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) was also used to study the morphology of the samples. The images were obtained with a FESEM TESCAN CLARA equipment, which is equipped with a LEICA EM ACE600 metallizer.

N_2 adsorption-desorption isotherms were collected at $-196\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ as a function of relative pressure p/p_0 over the range of 0.01 – 0.99 by using a Micromeritics ASAP 2420 V2.09.02 volumetric adsorption analyzer. Samples were outgassed at $250\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 12 h under vacuum prior to each measurement. Specific surface areas (S_{BET} , S_L) of all materials were calculated according to the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) [46] and Langmuir [47] methods using adsorption data in the relative pressure p/p_0 range of 0.05 – 0.2 . The total pore volume (V_t) was estimated from the amount adsorbed at the relative pressure of 0.95 ,

while the micropore volume (V_{mic}) was calculated by t -plot method. The pore size distribution (PSD) was calculated by using the MP-method [48] and improved Barrett-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) model evaluated from the desorption branch, for micropores and mesopores, respectively [49].

The FT-IR spectra were recorded in a Bruker Vertex70 spectrometer. The measurements were made by attenuated total reflectance (ATR) using a Golden Gate Single Reflection Diamond ATR System accessory. A standard spectral resolution of 4 cm^{-1} in the spectral range $4000\text{--}500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 64 accumulations were used for spectrum acquisition.

The thermogravimetric analyses were performed using a SDT Q600 instrument, using an alumina pan, flowing nitrogen at 50 mL min^{-1} , and a heating rate of $20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ from room temperature to $800\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Measures were collected and processed with Universal V4.5A software associated to the analyzer. About 8 mg of each sample in powder form were used as initial mass for the thermogravimetric analysis.

XPS measurements were performed on a PHI Versa Probe II Scanning XPS Microprobe spectrometer with monochromatic X-ray Al $K\alpha$ radiation ($200\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ area, 25.0 W , 15 kV , 1486.6 eV), and a charge neutralizer. Spectra were charge referenced with the C $1s$ of adventitious carbon at 284.8 eV . The Multipak software version 9.6.0.15 was employed to analyse the recorded spectra.

Gas Chromatography studies

The IGC-ID data were recorded using a Shimadzu GC-2014 equipment with thermal conductivity detector and helium as carrier gas. Retention time data were collected using GC Solution software. Each zeolite (about 400 mg) was packed into a 12 cm length and 2 mm of internal diameter stainless steel column. Filled columns were conditioned overnight at $250\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ under helium flow. The probe molecules in study were injected as a vapor phase, using a microsyringe, in a volume of $0.1\text{ }\mu\text{L}$ under a flow rate of 20, 10 and 18 mL min^{-1} for ZSX, ZSX-J and ZSX-H samples, respectively. Preliminary runs were conducted to find the optimal operating conditions for the targeted separation. Thus, the temperature of the column for propane-propylene mixture separation was found to be optimal at 150, 100 and $80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for ZSX, ZSX-J and ZSX-H, respectively.

Methane, propane and propylene employed were of chromatographic purity grade. The recorded chromatographic peaks were symmetrical, and the retention times did not depend on the amount of adsorbate injected, indicating that the adsorption occur within

the Henry's law region. The adsorbate net retention volume (V_N) for the used probe molecules was calculated according to Eq. I [50]:

$$V_N = J \left(\frac{V_g}{m} \right) (t_R - t_0) \left(\frac{T_c}{T_R} \right) \left(\frac{P_0 - P_w}{P_0} \right) \quad (\text{I})$$

where J is the James–Martin gas compressibility correction factor, V_g is the gas carrier flow rate at the flowmeter temperature (25 °C); m is the mass of adsorbent in the column; t_R is the retention time for the considered gas; t_0 is the retention time for the reference gas (methane); T_c is the column temperature; T_R is the room temperature; P_0 is the outlet pressure; P_w is the vapor pressure of water at the flowmeter temperature.

The differential adsorption heats (Q_d), equal to the enthalpy for the standard adsorbed state ΔH_d^0 (within the Henry zone), were determined from the slope of $\ln(V_N)$ vs. $1/T_C$ plot, calculated according to Eq. II [50]:

$$Q_d = -\Delta H_d^0 = \frac{R[\ln(V_{N2}) - \ln(V_{N1})]}{\left[\left(\frac{1}{T_{C2}} \right) - \left(\frac{1}{T_{C1}} \right) \right]} \quad (\text{II})$$

where R is the universal gas constant, and V_{N1} and V_{N2} are the measured retention volumes at the column temperatures T_{C1} and T_{C2} , respectively. Accordingly, the temperature was varied within certain intervals, spaced by 10 °C, for each molecule and zeolite. In the case of ZSX, the temperature range was set to 100–140 °C for propane and 150–190 °C for propylene. For ZSX-J, the used temperature intervals were 80–120 °C for propane and 90–130 °C for propylene, while for ZSX-H were 50–90 °C for propane and 80–120 °C for propylene.

From the obtained values for the retention time, the separation factor (α) for a mixture of two consecutive components (1 and 2) was calculated according to Eq. III [51, 52]:

$$\alpha = \frac{t'_{r2}}{t'_{r1}} \quad (\text{III})$$

where t'_{r1} and t'_{r2} are the corrected retention times of two consecutive component in the mixture.

The surface partition coefficient at a given temperature, K_s , defined as the net retention volume per unit of the adsorbent surface area, was then calculated according to Eq. IV [39]:

$$K_s = \frac{V_N}{A_s} \quad (\text{IV})$$

where V_N is the measured retention volumes at the work column temperature and A_s is the adsorbent surface area in m^2 .

Results and discussions

Samples characterization

Figure 1 shows the XRD patterns of the synthesized zeolites. For all samples the diffractograms match the reference pattern of the X zeolite (PDF number: 01-070-2168) and no others zeolitic phases were detected. There are not significant differences in the position of the diffraction peaks with respect to the simulated pattern, reproduced from the crystal structure reported by Olson [53]. While ZSX-H shows fine peaks and a flat background, denoting high crystallinity, the peaks of ZSX and ZSX-J samples are notoriously broader. This is due to the smaller particle size of ZSX and ZSX-J, 180 and 190 nm, respectively, as determined by the Scherrer equation, compared to ZSX-H (600 nm). This is consistent with the scanning and transmission electron microscopy results, where a larger particle size was observed for the acidic sample (see Fig. 1S). The increased background denotes the presence of amorphous phases. The sample ZSX-H was obtained by modifications on ZSX, which suggest that ammonium ion exchange and thermal treatment to decompose NH_4^+ led to the fusion of small particles and the removal of amorphous phases, conducting to the creation of conglomerates with a secondary mesoporosity, as confirmed by nitrogen adsorption.

Figure 1: XRD patterns of synthesized zeolites and simulated pattern of Na-X zeolite.

N_2 adsorption-desorption isotherms at $-196\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and the PSD curves calculated by applying the MP method (micropores region) and BJH method (mesopores region) for the studied materials are shown in Figure 2. The studied samples exhibited different N_2 physisorption isotherms, according to the IUPAC classification [54]. Sample ZSX showed a reversible Type I isotherm which is considered concave to the p/p_0 axis and the amount adsorbed approaches a limiting value. This limiting uptake is governed by the accessibility to the micropore volume rather than the internal surface area. A steep uptake at very low p/p_0 is due to enhanced adsorbate-adsorbent interactions during micropores filling. In addition, at $p/p_0 = 0.9\text{--}1.0$ the quantity adsorbed increases indicating that the material is liable to adsorption at higher pressures.

Figure 2: N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms at -196 °C (A) and porous size distribution curves (B) for ZSX, ZSX-J and ZSX-H samples.

Sample ZSX-J exhibited an irreversible Type IV isotherm given by mesoporous adsorbents, as expected. The adsorption behavior in mesopores is determined by the adsorbate-adsorbent interactions and also by the interactions between the molecules in the condensed state. In the obtained isotherm, capillary condensation is accompanied by a hysteresis loop H3 characteristic of the presence of slit-shaped pores that correspond to the existence of mesopores. The presence of mesopores of different sizes can be observed,

ranging between 38.2 and 63.7 Å. The smaller pores could be associated with secondary mesoporosity while the largest are related to the template used (surfactant micelles).

Sample ZSX-H shows an irreversible Type IV isotherm with an H2 hysteresis loop, characteristic of more complex mesopore structures where important network effects can be appreciated. The very steep desorption branch, which is a characteristic feature of H2 hysteresis loops, can be attributed to pore-blocking/percolation in a narrow range of pore necks or to cavitation-induced evaporation. The observed mesoporosity is a result of the fusion of crystals in this sample, as suggested by XRD and electron microscopy. This material exhibits wide micropores and narrow mesopores of approximately 12.7 and 38.7 Å, respectively (Figure 2B). It is interesting to note that the volume of the mesopores is slightly larger than the volume of the micropores (see V_{mic} and V_t values in Table 1).

The textural properties of ZSX, ZSX-J and ZSX-H samples are summarized in Table 1. The BET surface areas for ZSX and ZSX-J are apparent, since the C constant has a negative value, suggesting that the model was not applicable. On the other hand, the adsorption isotherm for ZSX-H samples does not fit the Langmuir model. The Langmuir surface area was higher for ZSX in comparison with ZSX-J, which is coherent to the greater presence of micropores.

Table 1: Textural properties of the studied samples obtained from N₂ adsorption/desorption at -196 °C.

Sample	S_{BET} (m ² g ⁻¹)	C	S_L (m ² g ⁻¹)	b (mmHg ⁻¹)	V_{mic} (cm ³ g ⁻¹)	V_t (cm ³ g ⁻¹)
ZSX	466	-106.5	370	0.62	0.128	0.136
ZSX-J	163	-112.3	133	0.21	0.041	0.066
ZSX-H	444	2355.3	-	-	0.101	0.262

S_{BET} : BET surface area. C: BET constant. S_L : Langmuir surface area. b: Langmuir constant. V_{mic} : micropore volume. V_t : total volume.

The TG/DTG curves for the studied samples are shown in Figure 3S, while the DTG peak temperature and the associated mass loss are summarized in Table 2S. In all TG curves, a continuous mass loss is observed from 25 °C to approximately 250 °C due to the absence of distinct steps. It is possible to distinguish 2 peaks in the first region of the DTG curves:

the first is related to the loss of physisorbed water and the second to the loss of water coordinated to the compensation cations. In samples ZSX-J and ZSX-H, the loss of water at lower temperatures could be ascribed to the presence of mesopores which favor the water molecules diffusion. Note that in the range from 250 to 450 °C these samples only lose 0.47 % (ZSX-J) and 0.67 % (ZSX-H) of water, while in ZSX zeolite (microporous sample) the loss of water was 2.59 %.

The infrared spectra of the samples show the characteristic bands of the faujasite zeolite (see Figure 4S and Table 3S). The band associated to the O-T-O internal asymmetrical stretching shifts from 976 cm^{-1} in ZSX to 957 cm^{-1} in ZSX-J, while the band corresponding to the O-T-O external asymmetrical stretching shifts from 1050 cm^{-1} in ZSX to 1063 cm^{-1} in ZSX-J and 1070 cm^{-1} in ZSX-H. This behavior could be related with the mesopores formation as well as structural defects.

The surface of the ZSX, ZSX-J and ZSX-H samples was studied by XPS. Table 2 shows the surface chemical composition in % of atomic concentration. The most relevant facts are the observed expected decrease in the concentration of Na for sample ZSX-H. The binding energy values of the constituent elements are observed in Table 4S. The high resolution O 1s spectra can be decomposed into two contributions. The first, at low binding energy (530.9-531.6 eV) is attributed to lattice oxygen of the zeolites, and the second one at 532.3-532.8 eV is mainly due to Si-OH groups, or strong Brönsted sites Si-(OH)-Al [55]. Figure 3 shows the high resolution O 1s core level spectra of the parent ZSX and that of the protonic zeolite (ZSX-H). As expected, the relative intensity of the contribution at high binding energy increase from 16 to 26%, and also, this contribution is shifted from 532.3 to 532.8 eV. The binding energy values of Na 1s, Al 2p, Si 2p and Cl 2p_{3/2} are typical of Na⁺, Al³⁺, Si⁴⁺ and Cl⁻ [56].

Table 2: Surface chemical composition (in % of atomic concentration) of samples ZSX, ZSX-J and ZSX-H.

Sample	C	O	Na	Al	Si	Cl
ZSX	23.49	44.17	13.51	8.31	10.30	0.21
ZSX-J	20.15	45.69	13.24	9.69	10.91	0.37
ZSX-H	12.73	58.41	3.50	10.83	14.53	--

Figure 3: High resolution O 1s core level spectra for samples ZSX and ZSX-H.

Inverse Gas Chromatography at infinity dilution (IGC-ID)

Figure 4A shows typical chromatographic profiles recorded for the mixture of propane-propylene using columns packed with ZSX, ZSX-J and ZSX-H samples. All three materials were able to separate the mixture mentioned above despite the short columns used. The elution peaks of these species are generally symmetrical and well resolved at different retention times; taking into account the adjusted measurement conditions (see Materials and methods section). Propane is a light *n*-paraffin; therefore, it only presents non-specific interactions. On the other hand, propylene has a π cloud associated with the double bond that results in stronger guest–host interactions. Thus, longer retention times were observed for propylene, as expected.

For each sample, profiles were performed at different temperatures starting at room temperature. For example, for the ZSX sample at room temperature there is a very slow elution and the peaks are not well resolved, while at 80 °C the propylene does not elute. An adequate separation is achieved for a temperature of 150 °C. This behavior could be due to the slow diffusion of the molecules through the micropore system due to

confinement effects and the geometric factors associated to the presence of Na^+ as compensation cation. In the case of ZSX-J at temperatures below $100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the propylene peak is very broad, and for slightly higher temperatures such as $120\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the propane peak overlaps with the air peak. For the acid sample an adequate separation is achieved at $80\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, at room temperature propylene does not elute and at $60\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ propylene elutes but with tail. These two last samples combine micro and mesopores in their structure therefore the diffusion of the molecules is favored at lower temperatures. Besides the mesopores presence in ZSX-H, the partial substitution of Na^+ by H^+ also favored diffusion since there is more available space.

Figure 4: IGC-ID profiles for propane-propylene mixture separation in ZSX, ZSX-J and ZSX-H samples at 150, 100 and 80 °C, respectively (A). Dependence of $\ln(V_N)$ on $1/T_C$ for propane and propylene (B).

The values of the net retention volume (V_N) were calculated according to Eq. I and then were used to estimate the differential adsorption heats involved (Q_d) from the slope of the linear fit of $\ln(V_N)$ versus the inverse of the column temperature (T_C) (Figure 5B). The calculated Q_d values together with some values reported in the literature for X type zeolites are resumed in Table 3. The propylene Q_d values were higher than the propane Q_d values for all the studied materials and show to be similar to those reported for other authors for zeolites X in the propane-propylene separation (see Table 3). The preferential adsorption of propylene over propane has been also reported for other types of zeolites like LTA, ZSM-58 and CHA [19], [21], [22], [45]. The highest obtained Q_d values for propylene probe molecule correspond to the greater retention times of propylene by the three studied materials relative to propane. This fact could be ascribed to a stronger electrostatic interaction for propylene as a result of its higher dipole moment (0.4013 D) compared to propane (0.0863 D) [43] and its capacity to establish cation- π interactions [57].

The gas mixture separation in the studied materials could be due to three aspects: I) Size and quantity of micro and mesopores (adsorbent porosity), II) Shape and size of the probe molecules, and III) Interaction of probe molecules-active sites in the micropores (that correspond to the compensation cations) and in the mesopores (structural defects and silanol groups). The pore sizes in all the studied samples are larger than the kinetic diameter of propane and propylene (4.3 and 4.6 Å, respectively [58]), thus both probe molecules can pass through the pores and diffuse through the crystal. Therefore, in this work the separation does not take place by size exclusion mechanism. The separation capability and the differences in the obtained Q_d values for the samples are given by the interaction strength between propane and propylene with the active sites in the zeolites.

The active sites correspond to Na^+ cations in ZSX while in ZSX-H correspond to Na^+ and H^+ cations (once around half of sodium was replaced by H^+ , see wt. % in Table 3S). Such cations interact with the dipole and quadrupole moments of the probe molecules and the strength of the interaction being a function of their size, cationic charge density and concentrations, as well as cation- π interactions [11]. The polarizing power of the H^+

cation decreases by a degree of covalent bonding to the zeolite surface, thus the interaction of this cation with the π cloud of propylene will be weaker. However, the Q_d value of propylene in ZSX-H is only slightly lower than in ZSX. This could be due to the interactions that can be established between the propylene molecule and the silanol groups present on the surface of the mesopores. The hierarchical zeolite (ZSX-J) has practically the same amount of sodium as ZSX, but exhibits a lower micropore volume ($0.041 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$) and a wide mesopore diameter range (38.2, 43.9, 53.3 and 63.7 \AA). In this sample the slightly higher value of Q_d may be due to the interaction with silanol groups in the mesopores.

The separation factors (α) were higher than 1 for the three evaluated samples, which indicates that all the studied materials are able to separate propane-propylene mixtures (see Table 3). Thus, the best conditions for the separation at a level beyond the laboratory it is a practical question, as the three materials are likely to be good candidates.

Table 3: Obtained adsorption heat (Q_d) and separation factors values for propane and propylene adsorption in ZSX, ZSX-J and ZSX-H calculated from IGC data.

Sample	Q_d propane (kJ mol ⁻¹)	r^2	Q_d propylene (kJ mol ⁻¹)	r^2	α	Ref.
ZSX	40 ± 1	0.996	48 ± 1	0.998	2.8	*
ZSX-J	41 ± 2	0.985	52 ± 3	0.987	3.5	*
ZSX-H	40 ± 2	0.994	45 ± 1	0.997	3.6	*
13X	30.0 ^a	-	40.0 ^a	-	-	[1]
13X	39.2 ^a	-	48.5 ^a	-	-	[2]
13X	33.6 ^b	-	49.4 ^b	-	-	[59]
	35.4 ^c	-	53.1 ^c	-	-	
NaX	32.6 ^e	-	45.6 ^e	-	-	[25]
Li-13X	58.4 ^a	-	61.4 ^a	-	-	[5]
	39.5 ^d	-	63.8 ^d	-	-	

LiX	35.1 ^e	-	-	-	-	[25]
KX	35.1 ^e	-	41.8 ^e	-	-	[25]
AgX-I	45.6 ^e	-	-	-	-	[25]

* Present work

^a Determined from fitted parameters of multi-site Langmuir model for propane and propylene adsorption

^b Determined from fitted parameters of the Toth model

^c Obtained through the Van't Hoff equation for medium to high loadings

^d Determined from fitted parameters of Virial model for propane and propylene adsorption

^e Determined by gas chromatography from the slope of the strain line of the plot $\log(Vg)$ vs $1/T_C$

Table 5S presents the surface partition coefficients (K_s) of propane and propylene for the three studied synthetic zeolites at all temperatures. The surface partition coefficients of the adsorbates decrease while the column temperature increases as expected. ZSX-J showed the highest K_s values, probably related to a high residence time of both probe molecules on the material surface according to the higher Q_d values obtained.

Conclusions

Lowcost zeolites synthesized from rice husk ash, as a source of silicon, are able of chromatographic separating the industrial relevant propane-propylene mixture. Scaling-up this separation seems then to be an attractive solution to substitute the expansive cryogenic separation at industrial level. Textural characterization demonstrated the micro and mesopores formation in ZSX-J and ZSX-H samples, which render complex adsorption scenarios, while facilitating fast diffusion. The ZSX-J material showed the highest Q_d values which has been related to the establishment of interactions between the targeted molecules with the silanol groups present in the mesopores. The differences in the interaction energies and pore composition and features, as evaluated by inverse gas chromatography, lead to clearly separated retention times and then affording the separation factors (α) larger than 1, which anticipates that these zeolites are good candidates for this application. Indeed, the chromatographic separation results showed clear resolution of the peaks in all samples, with a preferential adsorption of propylene over propane.. Shorter time, keeping good separation resolution, is obtained in the acid zeolite (ZSX-H), which make this materials as the candidate for scaling-up propane propylene application.

Acknowledgements

This work has been funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033/, project PID2021-126235OB-C32 and FEDER funds. The authors would like to thank the French Embassy in Havana for the partial financing of this work through the short stay scholarship granted to Katia Borrego. We also acknowledge European Commission (HORIZON. - Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions VALZEO Project 101086354).

Author contributions

Katia Borrego Morales: Investigation, Data curation, Formal Analysis, Writing – original draft. **Daniel Ballesteros-Plata:** Investigation, Data curation, Formal Analysis. **Enrique Rodríguez-Castellón:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **J.A. Cecilia:** Investigation, Data curation. **A. Rabdel Ruiz-Salvador:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Giselle I. Autié Castro:** Methodology, Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing. **Tania Farías:** Methodology, Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

References

- [1] J.-J. Kim, S.-H. Hong, D. Park, K. Chung, and C.-H. Lee, “Separation of propane and propylene by desorbent swing adsorption using zeolite 13X and carbon dioxide,” *Chem. Eng. J.*, vol. 410, p. 128276, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.cej.2020.128276.
- [2] V. F. D. Martins *et al.*, “Gas-phase simulated moving bed: Propane/propylene separation on 13X zeolite,” *J. Chromatogr. A*, vol. 1423, pp. 136–148, Dec. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.chroma.2015.10.038.
- [3] F. A. D. Silva and A. E. Rodrigues, “Propylene/propane separation by vacuum swing adsorption using 13X zeolite,” *AIChE J.*, vol. 47, no. 2, pp. 341–357, 2001, doi: 10.1002/aic.690470212.
- [4] A. A. Kiss and T. D. Zivkovic, “Adsorption Separation Processes,” in *Handbook of Porous Materials*, pp. 1–70. doi: 10.1142/9789811223402_0001.
- [5] C. A. Grande, J. Gascon, F. Kapteijn, and A. E. Rodrigues, “Propane/propylene separation with Li-exchanged zeolite 13X,” *Chem. Eng. J.*, vol. 160, no. 1, pp. 207–214, May 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.cej.2010.03.044.
- [6] B. Newalkar, V. Nettem, P. Kumar, S. Komarneni, and T. Bhat, “Exploring the Potential of Mesoporous Silica, SBA-15, as an Adsorbent for Light Hydrocarbon

- Separation,” *Chem. Mater.*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 304–309, Dec. 2001, doi: 10.1021/cm0106466.
- [7] N. Lamia, M. Jorge, M. A. Granato, F. A. Almeida Paz, H. Chevreau, and A. E. Rodrigues, “Adsorption of propane, propylene and isobutane on a metal–organic framework: molecular simulation and experiment,” *Chem. Eng. Sci.*, vol. 64, no. 14, pp. 3246–3259, Jul. 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.ces.2009.04.010.
- [8] C. Grande and A. Rodrigues, “Adsorption Equilibria and Kinetics of Propane and Propylene in Silica Gel,” *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*, vol. 40, no. 7, pp. 1686–1693, Mar. 2001, doi: 10.1021/ie000901g.
- [9] S. N. Vyas, S. R. Patwardhan, S. Vijayalakshmi, and K. S. Ganesh, “Adsorption of Gases on Carbon Molecular Sieves,” *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, vol. 168, no. 2, pp. 275–280, Dec. 1994, doi: 10.1006/jcis.1994.1421.
- [10] D. W. Breck, *Zeolites molecular sieves: structure, chemistry, and use*, 1st ed. New York: John Wiley & Sons, 1974.
- [11] S. M. Auerbach, K. A. Carrado, and P. K. Dutta, “Gas Separation by Zeolites,” CRC Press, 2003, pp. 1366–1418. doi: 10.1201/9780203911167-27.
- [12] Y. Zhou *et al.*, “Self-assembled iron-containing mordenite monolith for carbon dioxide sieving,” *Science*, vol. 373, no. 6552, pp. 315–320, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.1126/science.aax5776.
- [13] B. Yue, S. Liu, Y. Chai, G. Wu, N. Guan, and L. Li, “Zeolites for separation: Fundamental and application,” *J. Energy Chem.*, vol. 71, pp. 288–303, Aug. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.jechem.2022.03.035.
- [14] K. Huddersman and M. Klimczyk, “Separation of branched hexane isomers using zeolite molecular sieves,” *AIChE J.*, vol. 42, no. 2, pp. 405–408, Feb. 1996, doi: 10.1002/aic.690420210.
- [15] H. H. Funke, M. G. Kovalchick, J. L. Falconer, and R. D. Noble, “Separation of Hydrocarbon Isomer Vapors with Silicalite Zeolite Membranes,” *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*, vol. 35, no. 5, pp. 1575–1582, Jan. 1996, doi: 10.1021/ie950495e.
- [16] S. Abbasi, M. R. Khosravi-Nikou, and A. Shariati, “Selective separation of propane from the propylene-propane mixture using pure silica zeolites: A molecular dynamic simulation,” *Chem. Eng. Process. - Process Intensif.*, vol. 184, p. 109294, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.cep.2023.109294.
- [17] H. Fu *et al.*, “Investigation on Adsorption and Separation Behavior of Propane/Propene Mixtures in Zeolites,” *J. Nanosci. Nanotechnol.*, vol. 19, no. 12, pp. 7679–7688, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.1166/jnn.2019.16773.
- [18] I. G. Giannakopoulos and V. Nikolakis, “Separation of Propylene/Propane Mixtures Using Faujasite-Type Zeolite Membranes,” *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*, vol. 44, no. 1, pp. 226–230, Jan. 2005, doi: 10.1021/ie049508r.
- [19] C. A. Grande and A. E. Rodrigues, “Propane/Propylene Separation by Pressure Swing Adsorption Using Zeolite 4A,” *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*, vol. 44, no. 23, pp. 8815–8829, Nov. 2005, doi: 10.1021/ie050671b.
- [20] J. J. Gutiérrez-Sevillano *et al.*, “Analysis of the ITQ-12 Zeolite Performance in Propane–Propylene Separations Using a Combination of Experiments and Molecular Simulations,” *J. Phys. Chem. C*, vol. 114, no. 35, pp. 14907–14914, Sep. 2010, doi: 10.1021/jp101744k.
- [21] M. Khalighi, Y. F. Chen, S. Farooq, I. A. Karimi, and J. W. Jiang, “Propylene/Propane Separation Using SiCHA,” *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*, vol. 52, no. 10, pp. 3877–3892, Mar. 2013, doi: 10.1021/ie3026955.

- [22] C. Selzer, A. Werner, and S. Kaskel, "Selective Adsorption of Propene over Propane on Hierarchical Zeolite ZSM-58," *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*, vol. 57, no. 19, pp. 6609–6617, May 2018, doi: 10.1021/acs.iecr.8b00377.
- [23] M.-E. A. Benchaabane *et al.*, "An initial evaluation of the thermodynamic or kinetic separation performance of cation-exchanged LTA zeolites for mixtures of propane and propylene," *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.*, vol. 344, p. 112211, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.micromeso.2022.112211.
- [24] M. Sakai, N. Fujimaki, Y. Sasaki, N. Yasuda, M. Seshimo, and M. Matsukata, "Preferential Adsorption of Propylene over Propane on a Ag-Exchanged X-Type Zeolite Membrane," *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, vol. 12, no. 21, pp. 24086–24092, May 2020, doi: 10.1021/acsami.0c01461.
- [25] H. W. Habgood, "Adsorptive and gas chromatographic properties of various cationic forms of zeolite X," *Can. J. Chem.*, vol. 42, no. 10, pp. 2340–2350, Oct. 1964, doi: 10.1139/v64-342.
- [26] C. Cao, W. Xuan, S. Yan, and Q. Wang, "Zeolites synthesized from industrial and agricultural solid waste and their applications: A review," *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.*, vol. 11, no. 5, p. 110898, Oct. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.jece.2023.110898.
- [27] D.-K. Nguyen, V.-P. Dinh, H. Q. Nguyen, and N. T. Hung, "Zeolite ZSM-5 synthesized from natural silica sources and its applications: a critical review," *J. Chem. Technol. Biotechnol.*, vol. 98, no. 6, pp. 1339–1355, 2023, doi: 10.1002/jctb.7380.
- [28] J. Cejka, "Recent trends in the synthesis of molecular sieves," in *Zeolites and ordered mesoporous materials: Progress and prospects*, *Stud. Surf. Sci. Catal.*, vol. 157, J. Cejka and H. van Bekkum, Eds., Prague: Elsevier, 2005, pp. 111–134.
- [29] M. Zaarour, B. Dong, I. Naydenova, R. Retoux, and S. Mintova, "Progress in zeolite synthesis promotes advanced applications," *Micropor Mesopor Mater*, vol. 189, pp. 11–21, 2014.
- [30] A. Khaleque *et al.*, "Zeolite synthesis from low-cost materials and environmental applications: A review," *Environ. Adv.*, vol. 2, p. 100019, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.envadv.2020.100019.
- [31] M. A. Klunk *et al.*, "Comparative study using different external sources of aluminum on the zeolites synthesis from rice husk ash," *Mater. Res. Express*, vol. 7, no. 1, p. 015023, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1088/2053-1591/ab608d.
- [32] C. Zhang, S. Li, and S. Bao, "Sustainable Synthesis of ZSM-5 Zeolite from Rice Husk Ash Without Addition of Solvents," *Waste Biomass Valorization*, vol. 10, no. 10, pp. 2825–2835, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.1007/s12649-018-0356-0.
- [33] J. F. Gomes, A. Sachse, J. R. Gregório, K. Bernardo-Gusmão, and A. J. Schwanke, "Sustainable Synthesis of Hierarchical MWW Zeolites Using Silica from an Agro-industrial Waste, Rice Husk Ash," *Cryst. Growth Des.*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 178–188, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1021/acs.cgd.9b00974.
- [34] E.-P. Ng, H. Awala, K.-H. Tan, F. Adam, R. Retoux, and S. Mintova, "EMT-type zeolite nanocrystals synthesized from rice husk," *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* 204 2015 204–209, vol. 204, pp. 204–209, 2015.
- [35] K. Borrego-Morales *et al.*, "Low cost synthesis and characterization of hierarchical zeolites from silicon natural sources for environmental applications," *Acta Microsc.*, vol. 27, no. 3, pp. 189–195, 2018.
- [36] S. Lopez-Orozco, A. Inayat, A. Schwab, T. Selvam, and W. Schwieger, "Zeolitic Materials with Hierarchical Porous Structures," *Adv. Mater.*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 2602–2615, 2011.

- [37] J. Pérez-Ramírez, C. H. Christensen, K. Egeblad, C. H. Christensen, and J. C. Groen, "Hierarchical zeolites: enhanced utilisation of microporous crystals in catalysis by advances in materials design," *Chem Soc Rev*, vol. 37, pp. 2530–2542, 2008.
- [38] D. Verboekend *et al.*, "Synthesis, characterisation, and catalytic evaluation of hierarchical faujasite zeolites: milestones, challenges, and future directions," *Chem Soc Rev*, vol. 45, pp. 3331–3352, 2016.
- [39] A. V. Kiselev and Y. I. Yashin, *Gas-Adsorption Chromatography*. Springer, 2013.
- [40] D. R. Lloyd, T. C. Ward, and H. P. Schreiber, *Inverse Gas Chromatography*. in 391. Washington DC, USA: Am. Chem. Soc., 1984.
- [41] G. Autie-Castro *et al.*, "Adsorption and separation of light alkane hydrocarbons by porous hexacyanocobaltates (III)," *Surf. Interface Anal.*, vol. 41, no. 9, pp. 730–734, 2009, doi: 10.1002/sia.3080.
- [42] G. Autie-Castro *et al.*, "Adsorption and separation of propane and propylene by porous hexacyanometallates," *Appl. Surf. Sci.*, vol. 257, no. 7, pp. 2461–2466, Jan. 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.apsusc.2010.10.003.
- [43] G. Autie-Castro, M. A. Autie, E. Rodríguez-Castellón, C. Aguirre, and E. Reguera, "Cu-BTC and Fe-BTC metal-organic frameworks: Role of the materials structural features on their performance for volatile hydrocarbons separation," *Colloids Surf. Physicochem. Eng. Asp.*, vol. 481, pp. 351–357, Sep. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.colsurfa.2015.05.044.
- [44] A. Rivera *et al.*, "Acid natural clinoptilolite: Structural properties against adsorption/separation of n-paraffins," *J Colloid Interf Sci*, vol. 360, pp. 220–226, 2011.
- [45] J. Wang *et al.*, "Pure Silica with Ordered Silanols for Propylene/Propane Adsorptive Separation Unraveled by Three-Dimensional Electron Diffraction," *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, vol. 145, no. 12, pp. 6853–6860, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.1021/jacs.2c13847.
- [46] S. Brunauer, P. H. Emmett, and E. Teller, "Adsorption of gases in multimolecular layers," *J Am Chem Soc*, vol. 60, pp. 309–319, 1938, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja01269a023>.
- [47] I. Langmuir, "The adsorption of gases on plane surfaces of glass, mica and platinum," *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, vol. 40, no. 9, pp. 1361–1403, Sep. 1918, doi: 10.1021/ja02242a004.
- [48] R. S. Mikhail, S. Brunauer, and E. E. Bodor, "Investigations of a complete pore structure analysis: I. Analysis of micropores," *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 45–53, Jan. 1968, doi: 10.1016/0021-9797(68)90270-1.
- [49] E. P. Barrett, L. G. Joyner, and P. P. Halenda, "The determination of pore volume and area distributions in porous substances. I. Computations from nitrogen isotherms," *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, vol. 73, pp. 373–380, 1951, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja01145a126>.
- [50] S.A. Greene and H. Pust, "The Determination of Heats of Adsorption by Gas-Solid Chromatography," *J. Phys. Chem.*, vol. 62, no. 1, pp. 55–58, 1957, doi: 10.1021/J150559A015.
- [51] N. A. Parris, Ed., "Chapter 2 Basic principles and terminology," in *Journal of Chromatography Library*, vol. 5, in *Instrumental Liquid Chromatography*, vol. 5. , Elsevier, 1976, pp. 7–18. doi: 10.1016/S0301-4770(08)61243-9.
- [52] V. Gold, Ed., *The IUPAC Compendium of Chemical Terminology: The Gold Book*, 4th ed. Research Triangle Park, NC: International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC), 2019. doi: 10.1351/goldbook.
- [53] D. H. Olson, "The crystal structure of dehydrated NaX," *Zeolites*, vol. 15, no. 5, pp. 439–443, Jun. 1995, doi: 10.1016/0144-2449(95)00029-6.

- [54] K. S. W. Sing *et al.*, “Reporting physisorption data for gas/solid systems with special reference to the determination of surface area and porosity (Recommendations 1984),” *Pure Appl Chem*, vol. 57, pp. 603–619, 1985, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1515/iupac.57.0007>.
- [55] G. Busca, “Acidity and basicity of zeolites: A fundamental approach,” *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.*, vol. 254, pp. 3–16, Dec. 2017, doi: [10.1016/j.micromeso.2017.04.007](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micromeso.2017.04.007).
- [56] J. F. Moulder, *Handbook of X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy: A Reference Book of Standard Spectra for Identification and Interpretation of XPS Data*. Physical Electronics Division, Perkin-Elmer Corporation, 1992.
- [57] S. Schmittmann, C. Pasel, M. Luckas, and D. Bathen, “Adsorption of Light Alkanes and Alkenes on Activated Carbon and Zeolite 13X at Low Temperatures,” *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, vol. 65, no. 2, pp. 706–716, Feb. 2020, doi: [10.1021/acs.jced.9b00948](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jced.9b00948).
- [58] J.-R. Li, R. J. Kuppler, and H.-C. Zhou, “Selective gas adsorption and separation in metal–organic frameworks,” *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, vol. 38, no. 5, pp. 1477–1504, Apr. 2009, doi: [10.1039/B802426J](https://doi.org/10.1039/B802426J).
- [59] M. C. Campo *et al.*, “New 13X zeolite for propylene/propane separation by vacuum swing adsorption,” *Sep. Purif. Technol.*, vol. 103, pp. 60–70, Jan. 2013, doi: [10.1016/j.seppur.2012.10.009](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2012.10.009).